

Why China Bid The Olympic Games ?

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ABSTRACT

As a develop country China hopes that by staging the 2008 Olympic Games will lead huge benefits to develop its economics' level. Due to some different finding whether positive or negative economic impacts in hosting Olympic Games. By using article reviews this research is trying to find out about the impact of hosting Olympic Games in China it is found that the Direct benefits include the impact of the Olympics on exports, investment, employment and indirect benefits including the host city to be businesses destination, transfer technology and knowledge and tourism. On the other hand, in terms of sport reformation, it is clearly revealed that China has long been reformed its sport management since 'Olympic movement' was introduced.

INTRODUCTION

Success of China to host the Olympic Games is not running smoothly. The issue of human right and democracy have been raised dramatically accompanied with the Beijing bidding process. It is revealed that the initial desire to be the host of Olympic Games was begun in the late of The Olympic Games are a monumental tradition and this event has become a symbol or expression of unity, equality, and glory. The Olympic Games embodies a significant foundation of national building and prestige. Hence, 205 countries are embracing to bid and are aggressively convinced the IOC (International Olympic Committee) to be the host of this biggest sport event in the world.

The success of China bid 2008 Olympic Games is not running smoothly. Many countries attempted to pressure the IOC to rejected Beijing's bid. However, by reforming its sport management and willing to build their economic lead China struggle to be the host of this mega event. As a result, IOC has convinced by Chinese National Olympic Committee and the IOC has decided that China deserved to be the host of Summer Olympic Games 2008. It seems to be clearly that the readiness of human resources and capabilities and readiness in managing sports event become the key factors concurring the bad international political images to China.

With regard to the issue, it is important to investigate why China hopes to gain from hosting the Olympic Games. There is increasing recognition that hosting mega event like Olympic Games can have positive economic impact. It is estimated that the profit of sport industry in U.S in 1995 is US\$ 152 billion, just over 2% of total GDP and places the 11th largest industry in this country (Meek cited in Ashton et al, 2003, p. 783). In addition, some facts arising from the study show that economic interests predominantly serve as a basis for the China to be the host of this mega event. As a consequence, to accomplish its desire to be the host of the Olympic Games China was trying hard to reform its management related to sport.

This essay will examine the impact of economical aspects of hosting major sport event like Olympic Games by showing the economical impact some previous countries which hosting the Olympic games and examine sport management reformations in China. In addressing to these issues above this essay focuses on the brief history of china bidding the host of Olympic Games, government policy related to sport, sport management reformation in China, and the positive and negative economic impact of the host of the Olympic Games.

1980s (Ong, 2004, p. 35). Moreover, it is important to be examined why the IOC has decided to China to be the host of Olympic Games. In his study, Ong (2004, p. 35) explained that the failing of Beijing first bid in 1993 was caused by some countries led by U.S objected China due to the accident happened in the Tiananmen four years before 2000 Olympic Games. This argument supported by Poast (2007, p. 76), he explained that due to the Tiananmen massacre, United State, European Union, and western human right organization sturdy contravene the Beijing's selection. Moreover, The China government was trying to offer their candidacy again for 2008 Olympic Games

after failing to bid for the 2004 Games (Ong, 2004, p. 36). It seems clearly indicates that the political issues strongly influenced the IOC in making decisions at that time. However, success China bid 2008 Olympic Games simply signified that IOC has shown its integrity and push it direction. Black (2004, p. 1256) stated that after IOC's president election decided that Jacques Rogge was elected to be a new President of IOC then he was trying to emphasise the main platform of IOC as a sport organization. Moreover, Jacques Rogge cited in Black (2004, p. 1256) in his speech convinced that the IOC is a sport organisation which is not involving politic within its activities. Moreover, the real desire of IOC and world community is to totally convey China into the Olympic movement. Interestingly, IOC argued that by hosting the Olympic Games it will bring the possibility to China to instigate growth and reform in this country. As a result, without doubt IOC decided Beijing as a host of 2008 Olympic Games.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

This paper is a qualitative research, in the form of a literature review. This paper uses literature review research by reviewing several articles that are relevant to the topic or title.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Economical impact hosting Olympic Games

Since the Modern Olympic Games has been held at 1896 in Athens dozen of countries become a host of this mega event which aimed to increase their economical sectors. It seems to be evidences that each modern Olympic Games lead to increase the positive economical sectors. Moreover, Burton (2003. p. 35) convinced that almost countries that bidding Olympic game particularly to the economic impact and visible representation of city imagery more than the value of sport or the Olympic itself. In line with Burton, Shoval (2002, p. 594) explained that it is believed that the inspiration of financial accomplishment in staging the Olympics become a tools for economic and physical regeneration and not merely for visibility, prestige or symbolism. Moreover, Preuss (2004, p. 234) asserted that the Olympic Games not just cause to appear huge sums of "fresh money" into a city, but also to hasten the occurrence of development by up to ten years. Andranovich et al, cited in Poast (2007, p. 75) argued that to be the host of Olympic Games is strongly affecting both national and local government to make an attempt to stimulate tourists' revenue, push the completion of public works projects, and probably almost essentially, acquire international media exposure. Moreover, Shoval (2002, p. 599) convinced that Olympic Games and other major events are used as instrument for transforming the image, reassuring economic development, revising declining area of the city. The transform in image lead to increase prospect levels of tourism and to compel the interest capital investments. For Beijing as the host of Olympic Games will be the gateway to built new economic relation (Preuss, 2004, p. 243).

The willing to improve economical sectors was revealed by Beijing Organizing Committee for the Olympic Games in its hoping by hosting 2008 Olympic Games:

If we get the game I thing it will be a very bright future, yes more money, more business, more chance to develop. The bid of the Olympic Games is a part of strategy of the government...a big plan. If the 2008 Games take place in Beijing the two plans of mass participation and the Olympic glory will be stronger and stronger. There is also a close relationship between the games and future of the city. If the games take place in the Beijing a big part of Beijing will change people can live better and air pollution will decrease. (BOBICO cited in Theodoraki, 2004, p. 206).

It seems to be logically accepted that the investor will get their market to promote their product due to large China's market and high profits' possibilities. Nowadays, China is not just classified as a one of the largest and fastest growing economies, but it is classified with one phenomenal growth potential regarding to consumer spending, and is recognized by low level of gross national income per capita for about \$3950 in 2000 (UNDP cited in Black, 2004. p. 14). It is predicted that Beijing will reach tremendous market that would attract Olympic sponsors and extremely large potential China television audience for about 1 billion (Theodoraki, 2004). In his study, Shoval (2002, p. 585) revealed that the sale of television broadcast rights and sponsorships by international companies have drastically increased in the Olympic Games during the last several decades. For example, by a new regulation from IOC that shift package for broadcast right The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) paid \$1.44 billion for package, on the other hand North American Broadcasting paid \$57. Furthermore, in terms of 2008 Olympic Games in Beijing, he estimated that television broadcast right and sponsorships will contribute financially of approximately 2 billion dollars. The significant economic impact was immediately shown by some countries which are interested to participate commercially after Beijing bid this Mega event. It is noted that some countries, such as U.S.A, European, and Australian companies have showed their interest to \$14 billion on infrastructure project needed for the 2008 Olympic Games in Beijing (French News Agency cited in Theodoraki, 2004, p. 206).

In addressing the positive economic impacts in staging Olympic Games need to examine previous Olympic Games in some countries that it might be basis why China struggle to host 2008 Olympic Games. The success of 1984 Olympic Games seems to be the new period in history of Olympic Games and become a trigger to some countries to win in the Olympics bid. It is revealed that by decreasing in expenditures of the organizing committee 1984 Olympic Games ultimately generated o profit of more than 200 million dollars (Hill cited in Shoval, 2002). Moreover, Gratton et al (2000, p. 28) revealed that The Olympic Games was held in Los Angles in 1984 has benefited from sport events which made a surplus of £215. The 2000 Olympic Game was held in Sydney has a significant effect to the economical sectors of Australia. According to Harcourt

(1999), the positive effect to the economical sectors of the 2000 Olympics consist of two categories direct and indirect. Direct benefits include the impact of the Olympics on exports, investment and employment. Moreover, he stated, dealing with export the particular affect attract tourism, sponsorship fees, media broadcast rights, and ticket sales. In terms of tourism, he estimated that tourism will contribute \$ 2.6 billion. It is revealed that approximately \$1 billion in value is received from sponsorship fees. On the other hand, he stated that indirect impact is Sydney will be business destination and be a place of transfer technology and knowledge. By quoting Anderson (1993), he estimated that the Olympics increase employment in NSW by 5,300 for about 12 years up to the Olympic Games is held. Thus, it is expected 2,200 people are employed outside NSW over the same period. Furthermore, the Olympic Game brings a significant impact in increasing Australia economic activity by 0.12 % over a 12 year period 1994-1995 (Hayness, 2001, p. 6). Interestingly, the winner bidding the Olympic Games has a significant economic impact was shown when Athens Stock Exchange reacted more positively than Milan Stock Exchange who loose in bidding (Veraros, 2004, p. 749).

However, a study that is conducted by Owen shown that there is no positive impact associated with the event like Olympic Games. In his study, Owen (2005) was trying to predict the economic impact to the city which following the staging of mega events. He stated that the Mega event such as Olympic Games, which attracts large investments from abroad are considered having economic impact (p. 1). However, he asserted that the positive economic impact is lasting only a short time, a condition is not stable that change over time (Baade and Matheson cited in Owen, 2005, p. 5). Moreover, he convinced that the "Olympic Games" require a lot of public money to spend on venues and infrastructure improvement. Furthermore, considering China as a developing country, he stated that the prospect of staging mega event like Olympic Games will have bad significant effects. It is believed that the costing of sporting facilities is predicted much higher and significant additional investments are required from absence of up to date. On the other hand, in terms of economic benefit in sports team and sport facilities, he stated that there were not evidences of any economic benefit related to sport team and build new sport facilities. For example, gross domestic product or employment was not increased in U.S by build state the art sport facilities and form new skilled sport team (Coates and Humphreys cited in Owen, 2005, p. 6). Furthermore, in his article he used the long term Olympic benefit or Olympic Legacy as another standard projection of economic impact. In terms of Olympic legacy, he explained that the legacy effects such as positive publicity from the game; attraction of business; increasing tourism after the game and infrastructure investments are not included into the economic impact factors, but rather considered as additional which unable to be counted as a benefit. Interestingly, he proposed that indication of improvement standard of living or economic growth must be taking into account on the legacy effects of Olympic Games into real benefit to the local economy. Finally, he was trying to classify Games into three categories in terms of urban change. Firstly, low impact (smallest in

amount of infrastructure investment); Games concentrating particularly on additional sports facilities; Games aims to develop further on building environment. Related to these three categories, Essex and Chalkey cited in Owen (2005, p. 15) mentioned that the ambition of China to be the host of 2008 Olympic Games tend more likely to be in the third category. Finally, he suggested that the benefit to China by hosting the Olympic Games is depending on how useful the infrastructure investment post Olympic Games.

Sport Management Reformation in China

Decision by International Olympic Committee to award the 2008 Olympic Games in Beijing is due to the sport accomplishment gained by Chinese's athletes; staging previous events successfully; and the reformation of sport management in China. According to Hong (1998, p. 150) the sport glory in China began when Olympic movement was introduced in 1912 which brought fundamental change. Fortunately, the Chinese people were attracted by the Olympic movement and the Olympic movement aroused the people way of live one way or another (p. 155). Furthermore, in terms of building the nations, he stated that the act of promoting the Olympic movement can bring into consideration the communist ideal and make strong the people's faith in communism (p. 160). Hence, the successfully in applying the Olympic movement seems to be triggered to China to be the host of Olympic game as The Beijing Organizing Committee for the Olympic Games said that:

We want the game because China wants to be more open to the outside world so China needs to the Olympic Games. Our motto is new Beijing-Great Olympics. Now more and more Chinese like the Olympic movement and the Olympic movement is good for the people to be involved with...it is a good education (BOBICO cited by Theodoraki, 2004, p. 206).

The ambition of China to bid the Olympic Games was begun at the late 1980s, because of failed China continued to join this mega event's election in November 1998 (Ong, 2004, p. 35). It is believed that along with effort to bid Olympic Games Chinese trying to make up its management related to sport. It is revealed, that the way of the Chinese government reform it's sport management by which reducing personal expenses and increasing the efficiency of Chinese government, National Sport Committee to manage more the development of the Chinese's elite athlete in an effective way (Tan et al., 2008, p. 317). In line with Tan, Bosscher et al, (2006, p. 186) said that the increasing on national system and its effectiveness of utilising all relevant resources for the benefit of elite athlete have important role to the success of an athlete or team. By quoted Hong, Theodoraki (2004, p. 196) explained that the reformation of sport management began in 1993 when Chinese's sport minister announced that it is needed to reform sport management immediately. Moreover, he stated that an elaborate and systematic form to reform was to commercialise sport and create sport as a lifestyle. To achieve those goals China's government then through The National Programme for Physical Fitness

brings national project called “fitness for all” for economic development benefit, to increase the value of overall fitness and nation’s health (Reekie cited in Theodoraki, 2004, p. 196). Eventually, the aim of “fitness for all” is to address the well-balanced a significant consequence of sport; to rise to a higher degree of physical and health level of all Chinese people; build the national system of human’s physical health. Furthermore, to reach those purposes each council has specific administrative which also built in local government at different stages, from county to provincial government (Hong, 1998, p. 157). This project eventually brings huge effects for sport conditions in China.

Moreover, in terms of commercialism of sport, Theodoraki (2004, p. 196) explained that commercialization in sport were including people paying for sports and exercise, privately sponsored sport, encouragement the growth and development of a club system and advertising of the sport commercial market. As a result, a highly centralised organization was built to administer and supervise sport activities. Furthermore, the Commercialisation of sport was indicted by increasing sport administrators, coaches, and players in the same manner are financially rewarded on the basis of performance in provision, national, and international competitions (p. 197). By cited Reekie, He mentioned three keys aspects in reformation of sport as sport policy issues, sport organisation, and sport management. In terms of sport policy, physical education in China moved from a gold medal achievement orientation to more balanced view of professional sport and mass fitness. In terms of sport organization, sport and physical education will be supervised by the government, but the specific role will be conducted to professional organization, society and the community. As a consequence, sport and fitness will change to be industry and to be marketable commodity (p. 196). In terms of sport management, it is expected that administrative style change from administration based on experience to administration based on science, and formal regulation and law administration’s basis (p. 197). Interestingly, in his article he stated that the success of sport management in China based on long-term planning which is conducted within 15 years development program for sport industry from 1995 - 2010.

1. By the end of 20th century, the sport industry should be roughly established, while various forms of ownership are allowed.
2. Develop the sport fitness and entertainment market, the sport performance market, the sport human resource market, the sport technology and information market, the domestic and the international sports markets.
3. Encourage sport organization to be successful in raising resources, gradually reducing the financial support from the government and becoming financially independent. Those organizations should return a certain part of their income to the state (Theodoraki, 2004, p.203)

Tan et al, (2008, p. 314) explained that remarkable achievement on the 1984 Olympic Games with 15 gold medals was places China in the big fourth world rank have a detrimental impact to try to make an effort to develop elite sport

and make China super power in the world. The active participation in regional sport organizations, such Asian Games other world championships seem to be the way to reach the bigger event like Olympic Games. It is considered that China played their role in sport world just began when they participated in the Asian Games and China was the one pioneer from four finding countries (Hong, 2005, p. 479). Moreover, the great attainment of the elite Chinese athletes in some international events, such as the world volleyball championship, the 1982 Asian Games and the 1984 Olympic games which brought the phrase 'competition' the Chinese (Hong, 1998, p. 154). It is important to be noticed that China is the sporting leading countries in Asia which is counting as the largest continent all over the world (Hong, 2005, p. 515). Moreover, the position of China as a sports super power in Asia was proved by hosting 1990 Asian Games which is followed by 7 countries, with 6,500 athletes, coach, and sports official participated in the games. These evidences above have indicated that china has been tremendously reformed management related to sport. Interestingly, Hong (1989, p. 161) mentioned that China won 121 international championships and broke 99 world records from period of 1979 to 1984. Amazingly, in the Olympic Games held in Los Angeles at 1984, China gained the victory with 15 gold medals. In the 1990 Beijing Asia Games, China reached over 60 % of gold medals, 183 gold medals and the overall number of gold was 341. Furthermore, the success of China's sport performance can be seen in the numbers of medal from five times participating in the Olympic Games (Los Angeles 2004, Seoul 1988, Barcelona 1992, Atlanta 1996, Sydney 2000, Athens 2004) (Table 1).

Table 1 The China's Medal performance in the last six Summer Olympic Games

Games	Gold	Silver	Bronze	Total
Athens 2004	32	17	14	63
Sydney 2000	28	16	15	59
Atlanta 1996	16	16	12	50
Barcelona 1992	16	22	16	54
Soul 1988	5	11	12	28
Los Angeles 1984	15	8	9	32

Source: (Chinatown-online 2004 cited in Theodoraki, p. 200)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The struggle of Beijing and some other countries to be the host of 2008 Olympic Games has shown us that the Olympic has outstanding values to reach national goals. As a develop country China hopes that by staging the 2008 Olympic Games will lead huge benefits to develop its economics' level. Although there are some different finding whether positive or negative economic impacts in hosting Olympic Games, It is believed that by hosting Olympic Games will have significant contributions to develop economic aspects, such as direct and indirect positive economic impact. Direct benefits include the impact of the Olympics on exports, investment and employment and indirect benefits including the host city to be businesses destination, transfer technology and knowledge and tourism. On the other hand, in terms of sport reformation, it is clearly revealed that China has long been reformed its sport management since 'Olympic movement' was introduced. In reaching sport success the role of China's government's policies are quiet essential and lead to its sport achieves a great attainment. This achievement can be seen from its success in many competitions in Asia, and World Championships and Olympic Games. There superiority in sport was shown by China as the host of the Olympic Games.Ffinally, The success achievement will be continue and will influences sporting success to other countries in the region of Asia.

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